

Imagined relations - relational imaginaries: on the discursive interrelations of small towns in eastern Germany

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Abstract

Questions of actual and imagined relationality are still a gap in small town research. The paper closes this gap by focusing on the imagined relations and relational imaginaries of two small towns, Zeitz and Lauchhammer, in eastern Germany. Such imaginaries are considered as discursive constructs and are effective in multiple dimensions (e.g. flows of people, capital and infrastructures) and on multiple scales (e.g. local, regional, national). As such, they decisively shape the identity and actual development paths of places.

Keywords

imaginaries, small towns, relationality

Introduction

Despite the importance of small towns for Europe's territorial cohesion and economic development (Hamdouch et al., 2017; Mayer & Lazzeroni, 2022), they have not overall received much attention from regional development policies or scholars of urban and regional development (ARL, 2019; Bański, 2021; Bell & Jayne, 2009; Langguth, 2022; Steinführer et al., 2021). However, recent years have seen a proliferation of studies on small towns (Mayer & Lazzeroni, 2022), ranging from concerns with economic development (Hamdouch et al., 2017; Mayer, 2022), to demographic challenges (e.g. Steinführer & Grossmann, 2021), to issues of sustainability (Mayer & Knox, 2010), culture and creativity (Lorentzen & van Heur, 2012; Lysgård, 2016). Yet, there are still important gaps in this literature including questions of relationality (Porsche et al., 2021) and particularly the positions and perspectives of small towns in relation to other places, such as cities and metropolitan areas (for exceptions see Bański, 2021b as well as Bolik & Conradi, this issue).

Lorentzen and van Heur (2012: 4) state that small towns “are what they are through the relations they have and develop”, which includes their relations to other places such as cities, other small and medium-sized towns, and surrounding villages. The embeddedness of places in multiscale structural contexts, their multiple relations with each other, as well as the interactions of agents within these places and scales, affect to a considerable degree how such places are imagined and which kind of development local agents pursue (Bell & Jayne, 2009).

As small towns are usually “less self-reliant and hence more dependent on other places” than cities (Meijers & Burger, 2022: 24), their interrelations with cities and metropolises are here of particular interest.

So far, the relations between small towns and cities have mainly been considered from a metropolitan perspective within city regions and metropolitan areas (Davoudi & Brooks, 2021; for an exception see Terlouw, 2020 on different legitimising discourses in metropolitan regions). Yet, the relations between small towns and other places are not only defined from the outside, e.g. the metropolitan perspective. Small town actors are themselves engaged in constant processes of reimagination and rearticulation of such relations, thereby shaping their discursive as well as material realisation (Willett, 2016). At the same time, these agents refer in their discourses in multiple ways to economic, political, social and cultural narratives and imaginaries derived from and related to other contexts, e.g. metropolitan, national or networked (e.g. van Heur, 2013). Hence, it seems worthwhile posing two questions: (1) How are the relations of small towns to other places, particularly cities, imagined from a small-town perspective? (2) Which imaginaries about small towns are articulated and in which way do they relate to metropolitan discourses and narratives? Answering these questions implies also looking at where dominant economic and political imaginaries stem from, how they are taken up by local actors and how they are contextualised in a small-town environment.

For this purpose, the role of spatial and economic imaginaries in local development is examined (Davoudi, 2018; Jessop, 2012; Watkins, 2015). This is in line with recent calls to integrate a cultural perspective into studies on regional development, as suggested, for example, by the Cultural Political Economy approach (e.g. Jessop & Oosterlynck, 2008; Ribera-Fumaz, 2009; Sum & Jessop, 2013). I argue that in narratives about which kind of development should be pursued, small town actors deliberately refer to specific socio-spatial relations, either within the place itself (intra-municipal relations), with other places, e.g. cities, (inter-municipal relations), or with other scales, networks and associated imaginaries. These include actual and imagined flows of people and capital, infrastructures and the imagined functions of small towns as places of leisure, recreation and residence for present and past metropolitan residents, and also emerging discourses on creative cities or sustainability. Such narratives influence small towns’ identities and self-understandings of their role and position in the settlement structure considerably, yet they do not remain uncontested.

Departing from Watkins’ (2015) threefold conceptualisation of spatial imaginaries – imaginaries of concrete places, of idealised spaces and spatial transformations – I add two arguments to this burgeoning field. First, I claim that spatial imaginaries are inherently relational by referring to each other and interlinking with discourses at other places, scales or networks. Second, I add a fourth type of imaginaries, the spatial imaginaries of places’ various interrelations, which capture the imagined relations of places with each other, but also with other territories, scales and networks (Jessop et al., 2008; Jessop, 2012).

I look at both the imagined relations of small towns and the relational imaginaries about such places using the example of two small towns in eastern Germany: Zeitz in Saxony-Anhalt and Lauchhammer in Brandenburg. Both towns are peripheral in the German context, yet still in reachable distance of Leipzig and Dresden, the two largest cities in eastern Germany after Berlin, with over 500,000 inhabitants each. This proximity allows diverse functional interrelations in the everyday life of the towns' residents. Both towns are part of European metropolitan regions, which are functional networks that aim to foster the economic, social and cultural development of their regions. Zeitz is part of the Central German Metropolitan Region, which includes Leipzig, Halle and Jena, while Lauchhammer is part of the capital region Berlin-Brandenburg. Given these multiple interrelations, the places display a certain ambiguity. They are considered peripheral and rural on the one hand but are also part of functional metropolitan regions on the other hand, albeit with different effects on local development. Actors in both towns refer in their narratives about the places' development to the various, complex relations. This study draws on fieldwork conducted between 2019 and 2022, including interviews, participatory observation and document analysis. It adopts the novel approach of Critical Narrative Analysis to identify the imaginaries mobilised by local agents and embed them in their structural context.

The article is structured as follows. In the next section, I outline the concept of spatial imaginaries and propose its extension by two aspects: the relational character of imaginaries as such and imaginaries about place relations. The third section presents the methodological approach of Critical Narrative Analysis, while the fourth section discusses the empirical results of the two case studies. Finally, I summarise the findings in the discussion section and present three points for further research.

Spatial imaginaries of small towns – a relational concept in two ways

Nowadays, places are commonly understood as heterogeneous constructs that are shaped by their connections, relations and actors' practices (Massey, 2004: 9). Healey (2006) understands them as specific institutionalised nodes within the webs and networks of multiple and fluid socio-spatial relations through which actors and events are connected with each other. They are meaningful to human agents, yet the "social, economic and environmental meanings for those located in them" (Healey 2006: 526) may differ considerably. Such meanings are expressed by multiple stories and narrations of individual and collective agents. Places can therefore be understood as sites of negotiation and contestation which are subject to collective imaginaries and conceptions by different interest groups and their various (inter)relations.

Such collective conceptions of place and space are understood as spatial imaginaries (e.g. Boudreau, 2007; Davoudi, 2018; Jessop, 2012; Watkins, 2015). These are defined by Davoudi (2018: 101) as "deeply held, collective understandings of socio-spatial relations that are

performed by, give sense to make possible and change collective socio-spatial practices. They are produced through political struggles over conceptions, perceptions and lived experiences of place. They are circulated and propagated through images, stories, texts, data, algorithms, and performances. They are infused by relations of power in which contestation and resistance are ever present". Similarly, Boudreau (2007: 2596) refers to them as "mental maps representing a space to which people relate and with which they identify. They are collectively shared internal worlds of thoughts and beliefs that structure everyday life." Such imaginaries are used to give sense to and make meaning of the complexity of the world (Sum & Jessop, 2013) and play a crucial role in the continuous political struggles about and within places, including their constituting relations. They are used to at least temporarily fix a place as a specific economic, social, political and cultural space with an imagined community sharing specific interests (Jessop, 1997; Pemberton & Goodwin, 2010).

According to Davoudi (2018), spatial imaginaries can be characterised by various features. First, she understands spatial imaginaries as assembled background understandings (in the form of stories, images, memories and experiences of place) giving sense to, enabling and legitimating collective spatial practices (Davoudi, 2018). They help us to understand the perceived uniqueness of different places and their interrelation with each other and guide us through space in our everyday practices, linking our individual self-understanding of place with "the modern ideal of spatial order". Second, spatial imaginaries are emergent as they may start as ideas discussed in theoretical discourses "which, through processes of deliberation and conflict, gain traction" (Davoudi, 2018: 102) and then enter political debates and planning practices. Third, they are shared by a group of people and influence how a place is collectively "seen", "heard", "felt" or "read" (Healey, 2006). They give meaning to a certain place and thereby contribute to its specific identity. Fourth, spatial imaginaries are described as performative. They enable and legitimise material practices through representation while being also enacted and maintained by these very practices (Davoudi, 2018). They materialise in planning tools and practices such as plans, maps, images or scenarios, which represent and perform the future at the same time. Fifth, spatial imaginaries are epistemic and normative as they not only describe how a place is, but also how it ought to be. As such they might exclude competing ideas about how a place might develop (Healey, 2006) and cause the "othering" of some places (Eriksson, 2016). Spatial imaginaries tend to idealise specific models of places and hierarchies (Watkins, 2015) and thus reduce the complexity of the world to imaginative dichotomies such as "us and them", "top and down", "core and periphery" or "small towns and metropolises", and in so doing create easily understandable, albeit highly debatable spatial orders. Sixth, spatial imaginaries are contingent and dynamic. Past, present and future are inextricably intertwined with each other as "different visions of the future will lead to the mobilization of the past in different ways" (Garud et al., 2010: 768) and consequently to different actions in the present. Massey, (1995: 186, emphasis in original) ties up the identity

of places to “the *histories* which are told of them, *how* those histories are told, and which history turns out to be dominant”. Thus, there is a multitude of potential histories about places to be told which are actively built in the present and potentially also relate a locale to other places (Massey, 1995).

This temporal relationality points to an evolutionary understanding of imaginaries and narratives which are subject to the mechanisms of variation, selection and retention (Sum & Jessop, 2013). Narratives and imaginaries are fluid, dynamic and contingent, and multiple variants of them may emerge in different time-space envelopes. However, only a limited number are selected by various agents and, finally, retained and sedimented in dominant discourses. They might gain material transformative force which leads to changes in the natural and social world. The domination of certain narratives about a place’s past and its links to the present and potential future(s) depends on the exercise of specific power relations (Massey, 1995: 190) and the prevailing imaginaries at a certain moment in time.

On the one hand, imaginaries can hence be understood as constitutive elements of human agency which “prefigure material action through providing justifying narratives” (Watkins, 2015: 515). Jessop and Oosterlynck (2008) as well as Sum and Jessop (2013) describe them as semiotic orders that can be voluntarily chosen by agents to deliver specific interpretations of the world and provide legitimisation for particular material actions. They base their conceptualisation on a critical realist perspective, arguing that the existing real world is too complex to be grasped in its full complexity and that we can only know parts of it, which are the empirically observed actualisations of the latent potentialities inherent to all social relations (Sum & Jessop, 2013). In this sense, “imaginaries influence materiality through ‘stages’, proceeding from a semiotic existence to ‘selection’ then ‘translation’ into specific material [and observable] practices” (Watkins, 2015: 515). These processes of selection and translation are marked by specific human agency whose outcomes materialise in concrete actions.

On the other hand, the specific socio-material entanglements of agents also shape their capacity to develop and articulate spatial imaginaries and formulate options and visions for a place’s future (Garud et al., 2010). Hence, they are structurally constrained and subject to specific strategic selectivities (Jessop & Oosterlynck, 2008; Pemberton & Goodwin, 2010). Places gather both meanings and materialities which are articulated and realised by peoples’ practices (Cresswell, 2004). As a place is embedded in multiple networks and time–space relations, dominant local spatial imaginaries might be affected by the diffusion of alternative narratives and practices. Controlling them brings about political advantage and shapes agents’ capacities “to frame political processes according to one’s view” (Groth, 2019: 2). Hence, spatial imaginaries can be displaced, rediscovered or rearticulated over time through processes of resistance, contestation and change (Healey, 2006). The study of narratives offers a useful entry point to show how different and at times divergent spatial imaginaries are

mediated and negotiated in political arenas and everyday life, in terms of how they interrelate with each other and how they are contested.

The relational nature of the spatial imaginaries of small towns

Spatial imaginaries are of relational nature in several ways. First, they emerge from and are defined by the relations of local residents and outsiders to a specific locality, region or territory. People bring in their own experiences and biographic backgrounds and relate them to the place of action (Huggins & Thompson, 2019). Second, they are produced and diffused on all spatial scales from the local to the global (Jessop, 2012) and have the ability to move across time and space through a range of mediums such as images, written texts or material practices (Watkins, 2015). Third, imaginaries of concrete and unique places are shaped by and interrelate with spatial imaginaries of idealised spaces, providing general stories about the universal characteristics of places (e.g. global cities, but also small towns, left behind places or old-industrial towns), as well as imaginaries of spatial transformation telling general stories about how places have, should or even will develop in future (Watkins, 2015). Such imaginaries about idealised spaces or spatial transformation can evoke either positive or negative associations and support arguments either for a continuation of the development of specific places (in the case of positive associations) or for a change from a negatively labelled space into something else. If negatively conceived, such imaginaries may also lead to a continued stigmatisation of places (Bürk, 2013) or to one-size-fits-all measures that ultimately fail to deliver the expected results (Pugalis & Bentley, 2014). A recent contribution on the imaginary of “left behind places” shows quite impressively how such ascriptions may stick to places, enabling specific development options and foreclosing others (Pike et al., 2023). On the other hand, such imaginaries may also be explicitly mobilised to attract attention by policymakers and media representatives alike and open up new options for action or funding (Plüschke-Altöf, 2018).

Similarly to Watkins (2015), O’Dowd & Komarova (2013) distinguish in their work on the narrative articulations of imaginaries between “ontological narratives”, which are constructed within and with reference to specific places, and more general “meta-narratives” by which cities are typologised and “paradigm” or “exemplary” cities designed. O’Dowd and Komarova (2013: 540) state as well that the diverse narratives, which are often internally complex and contradictory, engage in a relational dialogue that mutually shapes their (re-)articulation and sometimes even overlaps in parts.

To sum up, imaginaries and narratives are multiple, interrelated with each other and “exist at different sites and scales of action – from individual agents to world society” (Jessop 2012: 8). They are an integral part of decision-making processes and strategic actions and point towards regional and local futures (Lorentzen & van Heur, 2012).

The imaginative nature of the interrelations of small towns

Besides the three types of spatial imaginaries that Watkins (2015) distinguishes (imaginaries of concrete places, idealised spaces and spatial transformations), the relations of places to other territories, places, scales and networks (Jessop et al., 2008) are also of imaginative nature (see e.g. Jessop, 2012). Therefore, I argue for the inclusion of one more type of spatial imaginaries, namely the imaginaries of places' multiple interrelations.

This suggestion is based on three propositions. First, the interrelations between different places and other socio-spatial relations are co-constitutive for both sides, including associated place-specific identities. Small towns in functional metropolitan areas, for instance, either refer to the city as the "growth centre" from which they benefit economically and demographically by flows of people and/or capital, or explicitly portray themselves as rural counterparts to a stressful urban lifestyle (see Bolik & Conradi, this issue). At the same time, the cities in metropolitan areas become increasingly dependent on complementary assets of suburban, non-urban or rural parts of the region to enhance their attractiveness and competitiveness (Terlouw, 2020). Particularly in the fields of housing, energy supply or recreation, the hinterlands gain more centrality in metropolitan areas, indicating the increasing importance of infrastructure imaginaries (e.g. Enright, 2022; Olesen, 2020). On the other hand, particularly small towns foreground their specific local identity in order to remain visible on the map and distinguishable from towns of similar size or bigger cities. Similar processes apply to small towns in more peripheral settings, which may attempt to benefit from their peripheral status by reversing negative images and explicitly drawing on the contrasts between urban and rural lifestyles (Plüschke-Altöf, 2018; Willett, 2016). Hence, the literature underscores both positively valued relations and economic benefits from (presumed) spillovers – or in other words a borrowed-size effect – and explicit differentiations between small towns and cities, which challenge agglomeration shadows (Meijers & Burger, 2022). Yet, the tensions between both observations are still rarely the subject of comprehensive research.

Second, since semiotic and material aspects of the world co-constitute each other, the imagined relations between different places have both a material basis and material outcomes in the form of infrastructures, inter-municipal organisations and forums, flows of people, joint projects, etc., which should be subject to research.

Third, local actors might foreground the importance of relations to specific places and scales, neglecting or devaluing relations to other places (and/or scales, territories and networks). This may be related to the development of other socio-spatial relations and a shift in power geometries, to competition amongst specific places, and also to the dynamic processes of shrinkage and growth of cities and small towns (Mace & Volgmann, 2018).

To sum up, the imagined relations of small towns to other socio-spatial relations are connected with questions of spatial identities, the co-constitution of imaginaries and

materialities, as well as shifting power relations in urban hierarchies. All three points are subject to empirical scrutiny in this paper.

Studying spatial imaginaries through Critical Narrative Analysis

The study of spatial imaginaries poses a severe challenge as they are mental construals (Fairclough et al., 2002) that are difficult to grasp and can only be approached in the form of their discursive and material articulations. Narratives seem to be a good starting point for the identification of existing spatial imaginaries. They bind together imaginaries, experiences and materialities, and condense and simplify them to something which can be grasped (O'Dowd & Komarova, 2013). This simplification is a highly selective practice on both the sender's and the recipient's part and thus contains an inherent political dimension the researcher should be aware of (Koschorke, 2012). Narrators have different choices to make regarding the start and end points, the perspective, the selection of events included within the narrative, material reference points and the different roles assigned to certain agents (Gadinger et al., 2014). All of these choices not only depend on the purpose of the narrator(s), but also influence the plausibility and perceived trustworthiness of narratives for the recipient(s), regardless of their actual truth (Throgmorton, 2003). On the other hand, the recipients' own experiences, imaginaries and choices in the reception process also influence their perception of narratives. Consequently, narratives might have different meanings for different agents, with in particular spatio-temporal relations depending, for example, on their socio-geographical positions and political orientations (Groth, 2019; Massey, 1995).

Critical Narrative Analysis (Gavriely-Nuri, 2017; Souto-Manning, 2014; Görmar 2023; 2024) takes these challenges and ambiguities into account. It combines the methodological approach of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) with a focus on narratives. Both perspectives have various features in common, primarily that they are concerned with evaluating social developments by focusing on processes of sense- and meaning-making (either through semiosis in general or through narration) (Fairclough, 2005; Jessop, 2010). CDA addresses development by focusing on the evolutionary mechanisms of variation, selection and retention. Narratives themselves comprise a certain degree of change as the basic storyline is about a change from a status A at the beginning to a status B or C at the end.

CDA is especially concerned with the relationship between language or semiosis on the one hand and social structures and extra-semiotic elements of social actions on the other hand, and this mainly on a macro-analytical level (Fairclough, 2013). Interdiscursive analysis as part of CDA additionally allows textual analysis to be connected to social analysis in a broader understanding. Narrative approaches can complement CDA's analytical tools for the study of texts with a focus on micro- or meso-levels (Souto-Manning, 2014) and offer an additional conceptual perspective on the narrative potential of texts. Narratives are constitutive forces in the construction of places (Roundy, 2019) and local actors' agency is revealed in the

intentional act of “texturing” specific stories and discourses in specific ways. Discursive development is achieved, for instance, by varying themes and topics, foregrounding or backgrounding specific aspects. Thus, it seems promising to integrate the analysis of narratives in a coherent framework to study processes of change in local and regional development.

CDA particularly calls for the integration of various empirical materials (e.g. textual documents and documentations of ethnographic research or interviews) in investigations so as to gain a deep insight not only into the discourses and hegemonic narratives but also into the institutional and structural contexts within which these emerge (Fairclough, 2005). The present study applies this approach by identifying the narratives in official municipal documents as well as in the transcripts of 47 semi-structured interviews with local actors in both towns. The material has been complemented by participatory observation at 24 events where strategic issues have been discussed in both Zeitz and Lauchhammer. The relations of both towns to other places or the relational character of local imaginaries were not initially the focus of data collection but later emerged as relevant thanks to continued theoretical work and initial empirical results.

This selection of material allowed a comprehensive analysis in three dimensions (see Figure 1). First, a descriptive analysis of the texts was carried out to identify narrative structures in the material. Here, the focus was on narratives and imaginaries that emphasised the relations of the two towns, including those to nearby cities and the relational character of spatial imaginaries. Particular attention was paid to narratives that have a metropolitan context as a point of reference. Second, by means of an analysis of the intertextual and interdiscursive dimensions of the material, similar narratives were bundled, differing ones distinguished and underlying imaginaries identified. These have been contextualised both with regard to the place- and time-specific contexts but also with regard to prevailing broader imaginaries and narratives (or in other words meta-narratives).

Figure 1 Critical Narrative Analysis (the author based on Fairclough, 1992, 2003; Gavriely-Nuri, 2017; Souto-Manning, 2014)

Imaginaries in Zeitz and Lauchhammer

Zeitz and Lauchhammer are two old-industrial small towns in eastern Germany which were heavily affected by deindustrialisation in the aftermath of German reunification and subsequent outmigration, demographic shrinkage and ageing of the remaining population. In the German context, both towns are considered to be peripherally located, although the nearest big cities are relatively close (see Figure 2). Zeitz is located 40 km from Leipzig and is part of the European Metropolitan region Central Germany (which also includes Halle as the biggest city of Saxony-Anhalt with a population of 240,000). Furthermore, it is only 20 km to the next central place in Thuringia, which is Gera (92,000 inhabitants). Lauchhammer is located 60 km from both Dresden and Cottbus, the “small metropolis” of Lusatia, and part of the Berlin-Brandenburg capital region, albeit on the very fringes.

Despite their peripheral position according to official classifications, the relations to the neighbouring cities as well as to other (smaller) towns and cities play a considerable role in both historical and future narratives about potential development paths. In the following, I outline the actual and imagined relations of the two small towns to other places, focusing on relations with the nearby cities without overly neglecting other ones. I show that these relations also differ in both towns, with Zeitz having much closer connections to Leipzig than Lauchhammer to Dresden or Berlin. Attention then turns to an analysis of local actors’ imaginaries about both places and the extent to which they can be considered relational.

Figure 2 Location of Zeitz and Lauchhammer (Source: Leibniz-Institut für Länderkunde)

Actual and imagined relations of Zeitz and Lauchhammer

Both towns are marked by multiple actual and imagined relations between different parts of the towns themselves (*intra-municipal relations*), their relations to other towns and cities (*inter-municipal relations*), as well as their *relations to other territorial scales and networks* (see also Jessop, 2012). In Zeitz, the most dominant imaginaries, those of the “industrial city” (Otto et al., 2012; ZZ_IN_04; ZZ_IN_21; ZZ_IN_23), the “ghost city”/“city of ruins” (Richter, 2017; Stadt Zeitz, 2019; Wecker, 2018) and the “city with open spaces” (Stadt Zeitz, 2020; ZZ_IN_04; ZZ_IN_13), relate to the core town with its heritage of baroque and industrial buildings, to processes of shrinkage and also to renewal. The core town and the villages that were incorporated into the municipality in the 1990s and 2000s have rather specific and tense relations. The villages often feel neglected by the core and only superficially incorporated in the imaginary of the town as a whole, as in times of tight municipal budgets, investments tend to be rather concentrated in the centre (ZZ_IN_15). Similar distanced relations between different municipal parts are also experienced in Lauchhammer, yet on a different basis. Lauchhammer itself did not evolve over time as a historic town but was founded in 1950 as a merger of four different villages (with three other villages being incorporated in the 1970s and 1990s). These different parts have been kept together by the lignite processing and heavy machinery industries which dominated the municipal territory until 1990. These industries

created a feeling of belonging and a joint imaginary as one of the centres of the GDR's energy production (LH_IN_04). After German reunification, the industries closed quite rapidly and their material remnants almost totally vanished, leaving vast open spaces between the town's separate parts (LH_IN_14). This led to a weakening in the spatial imaginary of being one town, slowly making room for the individual identities of the former villages (LH_IN_04; LH_IN_08; fieldnotes). Yet, the municipality continues to be one administrative unit. Therefore, the municipal administration aims to forge a common identity on the basis of a specific local industrial culture by claiming Lauchhammer to be the "town of art foundry" (Kunstguss-Stadt) (fieldnotes; see Görmar 2023).

Inter-municipal relations in both towns are imagined as both *cooperative* and *competitive*. This applies both to relations with towns of comparable size and with nearby cities. Lauchhammer, for example, shares the status of being a middle-order centre (in German terminology *Mittelzentrum*) with the neighbouring town Schwarzheide, sharing particular functions in terms of education, health and leisure activities, which is important for retaining these functions in the region (LH_IN_14; LH_IN_03). Additionally, the municipalities cooperate in the inter-municipal network of the "growth core of West Lusatia", comprising three other municipalities in the region. The growth core was established to develop joint marketing and economic development activities and to create a joint imaginary of a prosperous economic region at the fringes of the Berlin-Brandenburg metropolitan area. This has been successful in so far as the region is one of the economically strongest regions in Brandenburg (ews Sanierungsgesellschaft mbH, 2015) and industry is still anchored in the regional identity. Yet, despite this cooperation and the shared status of Lauchhammer and Schwarzheide as a middle-order centre, there is considerable competition between the municipalities in the fields of funding, infrastructural and economic development, including the marketing of their municipal business and industrial parks (LH_IN_18). In this competitive environment, Lauchhammer aims today to position itself by use of a new place branding strategy based on its tradition of art foundry and the related industrial culture (Görmar, 2023). However, economic actors also consider Lauchhammer's position as rather weak, calling for stronger links with Schwarzheide's development and a strengthening of regional instead of local imaginaries (LH_IN_03; LH_IN_16).

Competition is also one of the main characteristics of the relations of Zeitz to nearby towns, particularly Naumburg. The rivalry between the two towns has grown historically, dating back to the Middle Ages when the seat of the bishopric was moved from Zeitz to Naumburg for political reasons (NovoPrint VerlagsGmbH, 1994). In the course of the territorial reforms of the 1990s in Saxony-Anhalt, this rivalry deepened as both towns competed for the seat of the district administration, related district offices and cultural institutions. With Naumburg ending up as district capital and the closure of the theatre and several administrative offices in Zeitz, a narrative of always being the loser was established

among the residents of Zeitz, contributing to the spatial imaginary of a “town of ruins” (Stadt Zeitz, 2019), “ghost town” (ZZ_IN_06; ZZ_IN_14; Richter, 2017; Wecker, 2018) or even “left behind place” (Pike et al., 2023).

The *relations of small towns to nearby metropolises or cities* are of particular importance for their development, as in the case of Zeitz to Leipzig and in the case of Lauchhammer to Dresden and, although at a greater distance, even to Berlin. Yet, there are differences between the two cases. In the narratives of actors in Zeitz, the proximity to Leipzig, the effects of Leipzig’s development and associated hopes play a more prominent role than Lauchhammer’s imagined relations to Dresden or Berlin. Still in both towns, these relations are important. They are effective in both directions as well as in different interconnected dimensions, which include (1) *flows of people*, (2) *flows of capital and investment*, (3) *infrastructural connectivity* and (4) *inter-municipal cooperation*.

Flows of people comprise movements of permanent and temporary residents between small town and city, commuting as well as leisure activities in the fields of recreation and sports, culture and shopping. In Zeitz, the industrial period until 1990 was marked by notions of self-reliance and self-esteem (ZZ_IN_23) during which even people from the nearby city of Gera went to Zeitz for shopping (ZZ_IN_01). This changed in the 1990s and 2000s, when public attention focused on Leipzig, which offered better cultural, retail and educational opportunities, attracted big economic investments with large numbers of jobs and, after a decade of considerable population shrinkage, entered a period of growth from the early 2000s onwards. Leipzig and other cities were considered as the gates to the world, offering experiences which would not be possible in Zeitz. Zeitz instead was imagined as a “victim” and “loser” of economic and political decisions (ZZ_IN_03), with quite negative effects on the urban fabric. Growing numbers of housing and shop vacancies further exacerbated the feeling of being “left behind” (ZZ_IN_13; ZZ_IN_14; ZZ_IN_15). Similar flows can be found between Lauchhammer and Dresden. With regard to culture and shopping, Dresden has long offered the nearest leisure opportunities for Lauchhammer’s residents (LH_IN_22), as well as a large number of jobs at a time when most industrial enterprises in Lauchhammer closed and were dismantled (LH_IN_24). Hence, the functional interrelations with Dresden may be particularly important for local actors in their everyday lives, while political actors see the importance of both functional interrelations in the commuting area around Dresden and also the territorially bound political interrelations within the Berlin-Brandenburg area and the effective political decisions and regulations.

Today, the renewed growth of Leipzig and Dresden sparks hopes in Zeitz and Lauchhammer that they may benefit from population overflows. Zeitz is relatively well connected by train to Leipzig (a 40-minute ride to Leipzig main station) and imagines itself at the fringes of the Leipzig suburban area. Similar (albeit fewer) notions of being almost in the suburbs of Dresden are present in Lauchhammer (LH_IN_14). Yet, there are differences in

connectivity. Lauchhammer is 40 minutes away from Dresden by car, but train connections are rather poor, requiring at least one change and more than 60 minutes. Still, particularly the economic actors emphasise the good transport infrastructure and the beneficial location of the town in the triangle between Dresden, Berlin and the Polish border, which they perceive as placing Lauchhammer in a central position.

The hopes to profit from the cities' growth and development are not unambiguous, as it is still unclear if considerable numbers of people can be attracted to move from the metropolises to the smaller towns. At the moment, this prospect seems to be more realistic in Zeitz than in Lauchhammer. In 2019, the migration balance between Leipzig and Zeitz was positive for the first time for Zeitz with numbers marginally growing in the following years. A second hint to potential population gains could be that the last few years have seen new investment in the housing sector of Zeitz, driven by investors who are mostly also active in Leipzig and have recently discovered the town's potential (*flows of capital*). It is still a bet on the future, but some actors already speak of new housing projects by domestic and external investors. The aim is to reduce vacancies and generate a more positive image of the urban fabric in Zeitz, but this also brings the risk of real estate speculation and gentrification (ZZ_IN_13; ZZ_IN_23).

In Lauchhammer, there are two perspectives of imagining future residential development and the relations between Dresden and Lauchhammer. Interviewees from business and the federal state level consider Lauchhammer and the wider region as an industrial region offering high qualified work in new industries like renewable energies (LH_IN_20). Yet, management and other highly qualified staff are expected to live in the cities (e.g. in the north of Dresden), as seems to be the case today with managers from the chemical company BASF (LH_IN_23). Other interviewees from local politics and civil society portray Lauchhammer rather as providing affordable residential space surrounded by countryside and with a high quality of life for people who might commute to work in other places. The perceptions about available job opportunities and their effects on the towns' development seemingly diverge considerably, which could also result in different conclusions and development measures being derived. Interestingly, the official development strategies of the town mention the close distance to Dresden and its population growth either not at all (ews StadtSanierungsgesellschaft mbH Berlin, 2015) or only superficially as a stabilising factor for migration numbers (GICON Großmann Ingenieur Consult GmbH, 2021).

In Zeitz, the close connections to Leipzig play an important role in the spatial imaginary of local actors, not least in terms of interrelations with the creative scene in Leipzig. Hence, the need to improve rail infrastructure to Leipzig features quite prominently in local narratives, also in the context of potential finance being drawn from funds related to the lignite phase-out in Germany. There is a perception that a fast train connection leaving at 30-minute intervals would attract more people to live in the town and more businesses to locate there and thus contribute to positive demographic and economic development (ZZ_IN_11). Yet, there

are also fears that Zeitz will only be a “dormitory town” with residents working elsewhere and failing to form an active community (ZZ_IN_08). More economically oriented actors emphasise that Zeitz still needs to be a place to work and live in and that attracting manufacturing businesses therefore has the highest priority (ZZ_IN_14; ZZ_IN_15; ZZ_IN_21). Hence, the notion of attracting residents and creatives from Leipzig does not remain uncontested, as this is not considered appropriate compensation for the loss of mining jobs and the associated tax revenues for the municipality (see also Görmar, 2024).

Imagined relations of small towns	Zeitz	Lauchhammer
Intra-municipal → <i>Villages and core</i>	References to core town	Top-down merger of five villages
	Perceived distance in the relations between core and villages	Industry forged a sense of unity which was lost after destruction of industry
		New imaginary around the notion of art foundry
Inter-municipal → <i>To SMST in same position of urban hierarchy</i>	Perceived competition with neighbouring towns and feeling of loss	Shared status as middle-range centre with neighbouring town → Cooperation and competition
→ <i>To cities and metropolises</i> - <i>Marked by competition and cooperation</i> - <i>Multidimensional</i>	Benefit from growth of Leipzig Railway as enabling flows	Relations to Dresden or Berlin only imagined in the form of commuter flows
Relations to other scales and networks → <i>e.g. national and federal state government; metropolitan regions; institutionalised regions defined by funding programmes, and others</i>	Funding programmes set up by Saxony-Anhalt, national government and Europe Cooperation in European Metropolitan Region Central Germany → Zeitz as core area for the lignite phase-out (“Kernrevier”)	Different funding programmes Berlin-Brandenburg metropolitan area played no role in interviews

Table 1 - The imagined relations of Zeitz and Lauchhammer (source: the author)

A last point to mention here is the embeddedness of both towns in *metropolitan areas as a platform for inter-municipal and inter-sectoral cooperation*. Zeitz, together with many other Central German municipalities (e.g. Leipzig and Halle), businesses and higher education organisations, is part of the European Metropolitan Region Central Germany. Lauchhammer is located on the fringes of the Berlin-Brandenburg metropolitan area. In Central Germany, the metropolitan area positions itself as a strong actor in the current structural change process related to the lignite phase-out, as is also acknowledged by interviewees, particularly by local political actors (ZZ_IN_11; ZZ_IN_18). In Brandenburg, this process is more regionally anchored in Lusatia with a particular agency (Wirtschaftsregion Lausitz GmbH) playing a much more prominent role than the metropolitan region. In the interviews, the metropolitan region was not mentioned as an actor at all. In both cases, inter-municipal cooperation with cities across federal borders is rather difficult, presenting a challenge for the imagined relations both between Leipzig and Zeitz and between Lauchhammer and Dresden (ZZ_IN_08).

Relational imaginaries of small towns

The actors in both Zeitz and Lauchhammer draw on imaginaries of their towns which are relational in different ways. Culture and creativity play a role in both towns, albeit in different ways (for a detailed discussion of the role of culture in the narratives of both towns see Görmar, 2023). In Lauchhammer, the nickname of *Kunstgussstadt* (town of art foundry) emphasises a clean, artistic perspective on the industrial heritage of the town instead of the dirty image of lignite mining and processing. In this way, municipal and civil society actors deliberately aim to attract tourists and residents from metropolitan areas, particularly Dresden, to their town (LH_IN_06; fieldnotes). In Zeitz, the creative city discourse is far more prominent than in Lauchhammer and is always mentioned in relation to Leipzig. In this discourse, pioneering actors from the cultural sphere, but increasingly also municipal actors, imagine Leipzig as growing creative city (ZZ_IN_09; ZZ_IN_11; ZZ_IN_23), albeit already too “polished” (ZZ_IN_08) and with limited space for artists. Zeitz is imagined as a small version of Leipzig like it was in the 1990s or 2000s – raw, still unfinished, with space for experiments in arts and culture but also other economic areas (ZZ_IN_08; ZZ_IN_20; fieldnotes). Particularly the great potential of industrial brownfields and housing vacancies is reminiscent of Leipzig in the early 1990s. Yet, these potentials are appreciated by newcomers (from Leipzig or other places) and returnees from such places rather than by the permanent residents of Zeitz who mainly consider them as ruins (Stadt Zeitz, 2019; 2020). The official development strategy of the municipality acknowledges both perspectives and promotes an imaginary that takes advantage of changed perceptions of the town among young people:

Young creative people from the surroundings – particularly from Leipzig – acknowledge the potentials of the town and revive the cultural landscape.

They explore free spaces that are waiting for new uses – residential buildings, brownfields, industrial monuments. (Stadt Zeitz, 2020: 1; author's translation)

Yet, the pioneers who started this development in 2013 also see the town somewhat critically with respect to experiences of right-wing extremism (ZZ_IN_08; ZZ_IN_13; ZZ_IN_15) and the continued lack of an urban lifestyle (e.g. cafés, nightlife) (informal conversation at a local workshop). Many of them commute between both worlds, Leipzig and Zeitz, while other actors try to address this lack by organising events such as festivals and exhibitions or establishing alternative cultural spaces (ZZ_IN_10). Residents of Zeitz, despite remaining sceptical about the employment potentials of the creative industries, at least value the potential of newcomers and returnees to bring new ideas to the town as the biggest asset of the current emphasis on the creative scene (ZZ_IN_21). Yet, contestations of the “creative city” imaginary highlight the perceived importance of industry and the industrial heritage for the identity of the town, resulting in tensions with prevailing demands for increased environmental sustainability.

Another relational aspect is the potential of specific spatial imaginaries to position small towns against the nearby cities. This narrative strategy could be observed in both towns. With claims about Zeitz being a “green living and cultural town” (Zeitz, 2019) or the “green centre” of Lauchhammer, local actors portrayed their towns as particularly rural and green with big recreational potential (LH_IN_14; LH_IN_15). This imaginary is thought to be attractive for young families and people cherishing the peace and quiet of a rural small town. The green town imaginary is also linked to an emphasis on available space within the towns, seen as a contrast to overcrowded cities like Leipzig and Dresden (ZZ_IN_08; ZZ_IN_16; ZZ_IN_20). This issue features particularly prominently in narratives of local actors in Zeitz when they refer to the proximity of Leipzig (see above). In Lauchhammer, available space also plays a certain role in actors’ narratives, albeit not as prominently as in Zeitz. Consequently, local politicians especially emphasise the need to offer new building lots as a development strategy in both towns, although they already suffer greatly from housing vacancies (ZZ_IN_15; ZZ_IN_21).

At the same time, the imaginary of a green town also offers some potential for touristic activities for residents, particularly in the fields of cycling and water sports (ZZ_IN_07; ISEK, 2020; Imageflyer Zeitz, 2018). Yet, local actors also note that the natural environment is not outstanding enough to attract tourists from the cities. Rather, in light of current notions about the experience society (Miles 2021), small towns also need to offer consumption experiences and valorise on their (limited) cultural potentials like baroque buildings and castles (ZZ_IN_18; ZZ_IN_19) or industrial heritage sites (LH_IN_03; LH_IN_04; LH_IN_06). To attract tourists from other regions, Lauchhammer and Zeitz also emphasise the proximity of Dresden and Leipzig with statements such as “Here is the beginning of the new lake area of

Leipzig” (Stadt Zeitz, 2020: 136; author’s translation), again underscoring the links to the cities.

Relational imaginaries of small towns	Zeitz	Lauchhammer
Imaginaries originating from metropolitan contexts (prototype imaginaries) → <i>e.g. cultural and creative city; experience and consumption society</i> → <i>Flows of ideas</i>	Zeitz as a town of culture and heritage Zeitz as a creative city	“Town of art foundry” – industrial culture imaginary
Imaginaries positioning small towns against metropolises and cities, e.g. → <i>by promoting imaginaries of quality of life (green towns, associated recreational aspects, affordability);</i> → <i>by emphasising the “still unfinished” atmosphere of the towns</i>	Zeitz as “raw”, “unpolished” in contrast to Leipzig Zeitz as a small and green town Zeitz as an industrial town with continuing industrial activity and industrial heritage	Recreational potential of the town: → “green centre” vs. “hole in the town”
Overarching societal imaginaries of spatial development → <i>e.g. competitive regions, sustainable regions manifested in decisions on higher levels such as the lignite phase-out and associated funding programmes</i>	Economic competitiveness by increased attraction of the town Tensions with societal goals of fostering sustainability by e.g. post-lignite energy production	Regaining attractiveness with highest priority

Table 2 - Relational imaginaries in Zeitz and Lauchhammer (source: author)

Places, imaginaries and relationality: discussion and further avenues of research

Places are relational as are imaginaries about these places and their past, present and future development. Hence, actual and imagined socio-spatial relations of places matter in local and regional development processes, shaping perceived opportunities, challenges and measures to be taken. This is the essence of the research presented here and illustrated by the

examples of Zeitz and Lauchhammer. The relationality of spatial imaginaries is conceptualised in two different dimensions. First, I argue that all imaginaries are relational in that they refer, for instance, to imaginaries of “prototype places” or overarching discourses on spatial transformations (relational imaginaries). Second, I propose to add to current typologies of spatial imaginaries about places’ interrelations (imagined relations).

Both the relational imaginaries and the imagined relations of small towns contribute to places’ identities (Görmar & Kinossian, 2022) and may result in calls for social action and specific development activities. The case studies are particularly interesting in this regard. On the one hand, both towns are peripheral and portray themselves as rural in distinction to the cities. On the other hand, they have specific functional interrelations with the nearby cities that are part of local imaginaries. The integration of both perspectives shows the complexity of such interrelations and their effects on local development.

With regard to the focus of the special issue and this paper on the relations between small towns and other places, including cities and metropolises, I discern four different points concerning how this complex relationality plays out in development discourses:

1. Various spatial relations (intra-municipal, inter-municipal as well as inter-scalar and network relations) are the subjects of small-town actors’ imaginaries. In light of prevailing neoliberal discourses on the self-responsibility of places and local actors (Plüschke-Altof & Grootens, 2019), inter-municipal relations are often marked by both cooperation and competition. Towns of similar size and position in the urban hierarchy often struggle with the same challenges, such as deindustrialisation and outmigration, while their budgets are dependent on business and income taxes. To address these challenges, neighbouring small and medium-sized towns often cooperate with the aim of creating an imaginary that positions the broader region as a place to live and work in contrast to other regions or cities. Yet, on a microlevel, when it comes to the concrete location of firms or new development areas for family houses, small towns compete against each other, generating tensions between cooperative and competitive imaginaries.
2. Small towns’ relations to cities and metropolises are similarly characterised by cooperation and competition. Actual and (future) imagined flows of people and investments might be effective in both directions, often sparking hopes among small town actors that they may profit from spillover effects (Meijers & Burger, 2022). An important aspect of such imagined relations are material infrastructures like rails and roads, which should strengthen existing relations to the benefit of small towns. Yet, agglomeration shadows may also be strong, directing flows of people and capital primarily towards cities instead of towards small towns.
3. Local actors may deliberately adopt imaginaries rooted in metropolitan contexts and contextualise them with the specific conditions of small towns. Prime examples here

are notions of the creative city, the cultural city or the sustainable city, which were used in both of my case studies (see also the literature on travelling ideas and concepts, e.g. Long, 2016 on the example of Austin as a role model in the US). Yet, such “prototype imaginaries” (Watkins 2015) do not remain uncontested, e.g. by the notion of the “industrial town” and are part of constant negotiations about the future development of small towns.

4. Local actors use specific imaginaries to position small towns in relation to nearby cities and metropolises in multiple ways. In local actors’ imaginaries, small towns either benefit from growth-oriented developments of cities and metropolises or serve as counter-models as liveable or green towns with great opportunities for recreation that are unavailable to residents in big cities (see e.g. Willett 2016; Bolik & Conradi, this issue).

Local imaginaries of small towns are interconnected with broader overarching societal imaginaries about spatial development, such as notions of competition in a globalised world or sustainable development as a whole. Such societal imaginaries may result in higher-level decisions with consequences for local imaginaries and development measures in the affected small towns, like the German decision to phase out coal-based energy production. These imaginaries may also result in local struggles about which imaginary to follow (e.g. competitive vs. sustainable), eventually leading to contradictory development activities on local and regional scales.

The above-mentioned points cannot always be separated from each other as they interrelate and sometimes overlap. Yet, for the analysis of small towns’ imaginaries with regard to their relations to other places, particularly cities and metropolises, the extension of a current typology of spatial imaginaries by the notions of relational imaginaries and imagined relations and the use of the novel approach of Critical Narrative Analysis proves quite useful.

Still, there are some important points to address with further research. First, the present paper focuses on the imagined relations and relational imaginaries from the perspective of small towns. Yet, for a comprehensive assessment of this relationality, all perspectives (from metropolitan contexts, small towns and also from other scales) should be integrated with each other, enabling a more nuanced understanding of the power relations between them. Second, how imaginaries travel between different contexts is not part of this discussion (Long, 2016), although it is important to understand the potential tensions between different imaginaries, their role in local agency and the associated power relations. And last, the paper does not engage in debates about affect and emotions in spatial development, although imaginaries and narratives are closely interlinked with such behavioural aspects of local agency (Huggins & Thompson, 2019; Willett & Lang, 2018). This affective aspect of imaginaries creates resonance (Willett, 2016) between collective discourses and individual experiences, further influencing the evolutionary processes of selection and retention and the hegemonisation of certain

imaginaries (Jessop and Oosterlynck, 2008). To close these gaps, further research on relationality and imaginaries in small towns is needed.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank the organisers of the seminar “Small Towns and Metropolitan Cores: Functional Relations, Spatial Imaginaries and Cooperation Arrangements” by the ARL – Academy for Territorial Development in the Leibniz Association for enabling fruitful discussions and comments on the first idea for this paper. I would also like to thank my colleagues Thilo Lang and Markus Sattler on their comments. The research conducted for this paper has been funded through the project “Agents of change in old industrial regions in Europe” by Volkswagen Foundation under Grant agreement No. A126123.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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